

Empowering Community Engagements: Knowledge and Sustainable Management of Critical Raw Materials

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ABSTRACT

This study outlines implemented tactics and results for community empowerment through participation in questionnaire surveys, educational programs, and discussion on sustainable sourcing from new critical raw materials (CRMs) projects. Utilising questionnaire surveys, including the Public Participation Geographic Information System (PPGIS), the research gathered public opinions from Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia, receiving 1,068 responses. These responses addressed various social, economic, and environmental issues related to CRM projects. Feedback from educational courses with participants from over 25 nations and public events provided additional insights. The collected data and feedback offer crucial input for advancing sustainable and responsible CRM sourcing strategies in these regions.

INTRODUCTION

Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) are crucial to many high-tech applications, such as advanced manufacturing, digital infrastructure, electric vehicles, and renewable energy

technologies (European Commission, 2020). In addition, CRMs are essential for advancing technology, accomplishing sustainability objectives, and lessening environmental impact (Islam et al., 2024). In response to CRMs' growing importance in speeding up the world's shift to greener, more digitally-driven economies, the EU-funded AGEMERA project, "Agile Exploration and Geo-Modelling for European Critical Raw Materials," intends to contribute to achieving sustainability on the CRM value chain through multi-core initiatives (Islam et al., 2023).

Ensuring responsible, sustainable, and secure supply is essential in the EU. By providing a steady supply from local and foreign sources of CRMs, the EU can become less dependent on other competitive nations and gain greater strategic autonomy (European Parliament, 2023). However, potential and ongoing CRM projects face challenges like price uncertainty, broken supply chains, and erroneous reporting practices (Islam et al., 2022). Furthermore, the social license to operate (SLO) or social license to explore (SLE) plays a vital role in managing business risk during responsible sourcing from potential new CRM projects. Maintaining SLE and SLO is essential to comprehending

community, social and cultural dynamics, and local and regional environmental attitudes and concerns (Wajid et al., 2022).

To address local acceptance and sustainability of mineral exploration and mining, the AGEMERA project has conducted extensive public opinion questionnaire surveys in Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia, following a similar pilot survey in Finland. The survey has investigated social sustainability issues and general attitudes towards mineral exploration and mining effects.

In addition to the questionnaire survey, the AGEMERA project has developed university courses called “European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)”, which aim to raise awareness of CRMs and their importance in everyday life among future scientists and engineers. Furthermore, the project has invested considerable effort into planning, organising, and conducting several public awareness events, seminars, and workshops on CRMs in several European countries. These initiatives seek to clarify how these critical materials affect day-to-day existence, the viability of associated projects, the environment, and the processes related to mine closure.

The goals of the paper can be classified into three thematic sections:

- Give a thorough rundown of the actions to implement questionnaire surveys in the four case study regions – Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia. In addition, the key figures of the collected public opinion data have been analysed.
- Discuss and evaluate the results and lessons learned from creating and executing the “European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)” university courses.
- The last objective is to highlight the workshops, seminars, and public events on critical minerals and metals that were organised, scheduled and carried out within the project. This section emphasises the main points discussed, such as target audiences and goals.

METHODOLOGY

Questionnaire Survey Implementation

Multi-nation questionnaire surveys of local people have been planned and conducted to create a Geographic Information Systems (GIS)-based map of potential social, environmental, and economic vulnerability related to mining and exploration activities in the case study areas of Estonia, Finland, Germany, Poland, and Zambia. To reach the goal, several actions and timelines have been planned and followed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Timeline for open-access Soft-GIS database-based map creation (Islam, 2024)

First, a questionnaire was created integrating Public Participation Geographic Information Systems (PPGIS), including general and map-based questions, and tested in Finland’s case study area. After that, specific case study regions were selected from each of the four nations (Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia), with a privacy policy designed to ensure the protection of the data provided by the responders. Following the questionnaire and privacy policy submission to the Maptionnaire platform, a large-scale online distribution campaign has been undertaken to contact locals and collect their insightful feedback from each country’s case study area.

Besides the general questionnaire, Public Participation GIS (PPGIS) has been incorporated into the map-based survey questions as part of the project’s questionnaire approach. To make it easier for the responders, mineral potential maps were pre-added or marked on the map for each case study area in the questionnaire survey, for example, shown in Figure 2. It has allowed the questionnaire survey respondents to map important sites or regions

Figure 2. Mineral potential area with turquoise colour in the case study sites of Germany and Poland (Islam, 2024)

that should remain unaffected or appropriate for usage by the extractive industry. In addition, respondents had the opportunity to describe the reason or their thoughts behind the selected particular place suitable for mining and the place to be kept untouched.

Launch of Educational Courses

Developing and launching the ‘European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs)’ course series involves a collaborative approach among five higher education institutions (HEIs) worldwide: TU Bergakademie Freiberg (TUBAF), Tallinn University of Technology (TT), University of Oulu (UO), University of Lapland (UL), and University of Zambia (UNZA). TUBAF led the framework development, coordinating with the HEIs to structure and organise courses on the OPAL platform, Saxony’s primary learning platform, known for its accessibility and user-friendly interface (Figure 3).

The initial design of course content focused on the value chain of critical battery raw materials and rare earth elements, integrating up-to-date industry insights, and opened for students on March 4, 2024. To ensure participant engagement, the course design incorporated student and tutor roles with different access levels and live lectures in a virtual classroom to foster interactive learning. Recordings of live sessions are stored on the video platform of TUBAF and made accessible within each chapter for review. The OPAL platform also has provided dedicated sections for course navigation, tutor profiles to assist learners, feedback, attending pre-examinations with quiz questions and receiving automated certificates of attendance.

Organisation of Public Awareness Events

Public awareness events related to critical raw materials (CRM) focus on raising understanding about the essential role of minerals and metals in daily lives, sustainability initiatives, environmental impacts, and mining project closures. Key activities include organising workshops and seminars that target a broad audience, not limited to university students, but open to the general public. Stakeholders are actively involved, fostering open dialogue and constructive discussions. To gauge the impact and effectiveness of these events, participants complete questionnaires and surveys before and after each session, allowing organisers to measure shifts in public awareness and social acceptance of CRM. The overarching goal of these events is to enhance awareness about CRM’s significance in driving the green and digital transition, a crucial step for sustainable development and technological advancement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluated Figures of the Conducted Questionnaire Survey

The questionnaire survey was conducted in Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia in Spring 2024 and was completed with 1068 submitted respondents, 849 unsubmitted respondents, and 1100 bounce visitors.

Table 1 compares the questions’ specific submitted response numbers and the total submitted responses. Around 54–57% of respondents answered questions about their socioeconomic status, gender, year of birth, and degree of education. This suggests that the completion rates for

Figure 3. The landing page of ECRMs in the OPAL platform (Islam, 2024)

demographic and personal questions were comparatively

Table 1. Comparison between the total and submitted number of responses for the gathered data from the survey conducted in Estonia, Germany, Poland and Zambia

Themes of the Questions	Total	Submitted	Percentage (%) of Submission
Birth year	1351	753	55.73
Gender	1882	1024	54.41
Level of education	1830	1004	54.86
Socio-economic status	1820	1008	55.38
Working sector	1380	782	56.67
Informed about mineral exploration	1776	1016	57.21
Personal contact with companies	513	368	71.73
Benefits and harms	1498	1010	67.42
Effects of mineral exploration on other business	1057	753	71.24
Future of your home region	1397	1002	71.72
Least important economic sector	929	681	73.30
Biggest threats for 2050	1071	825	77.03
Mineral exploration's social impacts	1306	1005	76.95
Concerned about the effect of mineral exploration	1018	782	76.82
Local people's participation and influence	1263	1001	79.25
Compensation for the harms	776	624	80.41
Environmental concern	1014	820	80.87
Mineral exploration's effects on the environment	943	766	81.23
Environmental problems associated with mining affect views on mineral exploration	895	730	81.56
Source of reliable information about the extractive sector	657	549	83.56
Primary municipality of residence	926	779	84.12
Home postal code	759	648	85.37
Relationship with the area	914	779	85.22
Region Selection	802	686	85.53
How to find the survey	969	962	99.27

lower. However, the submission rates for questions concerning the primary municipality of residence, the home postal code, the association with the area, and the method of accessing the survey are very high, frequently exceeding 85%. Nearly all respondents finished the “How to find the survey” section, as evidenced by the high rate of 99.27%. This is probably because it was simple to complete and needed little work.

The submission rates for awareness and perception-related questions, such as knowing the effects of mining exploration, range from 67% to 77%. In general, more careful answers are needed to these queries. Conversely, inquiries concerning environmental issues, social consequences, and community involvement demonstrate excellent response rates, typically surpassing 80%. This implies that questions about environmental and community concerns aroused respondents' interest more.

The survey's respondents are divided into different birth year groups, and their distributions varied (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Year of birth distribution of the respondents (Islam, 2024)

With roughly 34.2% of respondents, the most significant section of the respondents' group was those born between 1965 and 1980. Approximately 32.8% of respondents were born between 1981 and 1996 and came in second place.

Furthermore, the respondents born between 1946 and 1964 accounted for about 29.5%. Finally, in the birth years between 1997 and 2012, the youngest group represented roughly 21.2% of the respondents to the survey.

Respondents provided gender information (Figure 5), with male respondents comprising over 52.3% of the total and female respondents comprising about 44.6%. Only 2.6% of respondents were uninterested in disclosing their gender. Nevertheless, with a slight male predominance, the gender distribution shows relatively equal involvement from male and female respondents.

In total, 1,830 respondents disclosed their educational backgrounds (Figure 6). With over half (50.7%) of the total responses, respondents with a higher education background comprise the largest category. Respondents with a college degree or specialised vocational training comprise 25.02%, while upper secondary education comes third at 18.90%. With 0.71% and 1.15% of all replies, those enrolled in comprehensive and primary schools are underrepresented.

One thousand eight hundred twenty respondents disclosed their socioeconomic position (Figure 7). A diverse representation is evident in the distribution of respondents across various categories: 16.09% identified as students, while 55.76% reported being employed. Retired respondents were 14.95%, while the remaining groups were 2.86% unemployed, 2.47% stay-at-home or family caregivers, 0.93% in the armed forces or other national services, and 6.97% other. This breakdown highlights most working adults and students, who comprise more than 72.85% of all responders. The survey data could shed light on the various viewpoints and experiences held by people in various occupational positions and their contribution to understanding the multiple themes of the questionnaire survey.

To see the overall view, 55.71% of respondents to the first launch questionnaire survey eventually submitted

their answers, according to the total number of recorded responses. Although 44.29% of responses contain numerous completed questions, the respondents did not submit their responses to be included in the project's research

Figure 6. Education-level of the survey respondents (Islam, 2024)

Figure 5. Gender distribution of questionnaire survey respondents (Islam, 2024)

Figure 7. Socio-economic status of the survey respondents (Islam, 2024)

evaluation by the end. The respondent's submitted answers will be considered for evaluation. So, the large percentage of incomplete responses draws attention to potential issues with the survey process and further improvement scope in the project's final survey initiative in 2025.

Map-Based Responses and PPGIS Experiences

The PPGIS questionnaire targeted four countries, and 750 respondents selected regions from Estonia, Germany, Poland, and Zambia (Figure 8).

Moreover, 52 respondents are from the Rovaniemi and Kuusamo, the pilot case study area of the questionnaire survey initiative conducted in the spring of 2023 in Finland. In the end, 686 respondents submitted their responses regarding region selection for use and count. Submission percentages continuously exceeded 94%, demonstrating active involvement and showing that the respondents diligently gave detailed information for narrowly focused locations and more general areas (Table 2).

Extensive participation has provided justifications in map-based questions in both categories: suitable for the extractive sector and should be left untouched. Among the 750 respondents, 213 participants responded to inquiries concerning the suitability of particular locations and gave their views. Regarding the questions concerning more

general areas appropriate for the extractive activity, 128 responses explained their choice of the selections.

However, more respondents answered the questions regarding locations to be left untouched. The 260 respondents who gave justifications for their decisions demonstrated significant public support for conservation and shielding specific places from extractive industries. In response to questions about general areas, 167 respondents explained their choices.

By facilitating GIS and enhancing planning through multiple kinds of local insights, the PPGIS approach has turned local people into local experts and allowed the project's case study researchers to identify the location and area-specific local concerns.

Background and Key Outcomes of the Educational Courses

In the first term of the course, 73 people registered from over 25 nations. Based on the e-mail addresses used by the registered people, Figure 9 draws conclusions regarding their backgrounds.

Out of the 73 people who registered, a great majority of the people (50) are students of TUBAF. Among 50 participants of TUBAF, 41 are part of TUBAF's Faculty of Geosciences, Geoengineering and Mining. Seven people enrolled from the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology and two from the Faculty of Mechanical, Process, and Energy Engineering. Two people registered for the course from UO, three from TT, and one from UL. Quantifying the number of students from UNZA was impossible, as they seem to use private email accounts. However, several students later identified themselves as students from UNZA during the courses. In addition, participants used email addresses that could be assigned to external organisations, partner companies of the project, and HEIs that were not affiliated with the AGEMERA project.

Figure 8. Number of region selections from different countries for the PPGIS questions (Islam, 2024)

Table 2. Number of explanations regarding suitable and off-limit for extractive sectors

		Total Number of Explanations	Percentage (%) of Submission
Suitable for Extractive Sector	Locations	213	94.84
	Areas	128	98.43
Should be Left Untouched	Locations	260	94.23
	Areas	167	98.20

Figure 9. Origin of the students in the ECRMs courses (Islam, 2024)

The online pre-examination, feedback questionnaire, and providing a certificate of attendance (COA) were completed on April 22, 2024, on OPAL. The online pre-examination consists of 33 questions, each worth one point, for a total score of 33. In the first term of the course, 33 participants took the online pre-examination, achieving an average score of 27.59 out of 33, corresponding to 83.61%. All 33 participants passed the pre-examination with a minimum of 13.2 points (40%) required to pass.

In feedback questions, respondents were asked when they were first introduced to CRMs. Most respondents (71.43%) indicated they were introduced to CRMs before registering for the course. Almost a third (28.57%) heard about CRMs for the first time during the course. Subsequently, respondents rated their agreement on whether the course enhanced their understanding of various CRM-related topics, and 86.65% of the feedback was positive ('strongly agree': 48.86%; 'agree': 37.78%). On average, 11.36% of respondents were neutral, and only 1.7% provided negative feedback ('strongly disagree': 0%; 'disagree': 1.87%) regarding the course's ability to enhance their understanding of various topics related to CRMs. In the following feedback questionnaire, participants were asked how ECRMs improved their knowledge of CRMs beyond the previously mentioned learning outcomes. Below, a selection of received responses is displayed:

- *"The process of how they are extracted and processed was new to me and I learned a lot about the different CRMs and their economic and strategic importance."*
- *"revisit the course and research further"*
- *"It is my first exposure to mineral resources to African continent. Second thing, the context of policies and regulations and amendment to CRMs was something I haven't explored until before this course."*
- *"I had a realization about the vast spread of the field."*
- *"to see different sides of the industry which is quite beneficial"*
- *"how important these materials are to key sectors of life."*
- *"A great update to know what's going on. Some stuff are not common in normal classes, so It was great."*
- *"There was a lot of new things to learn"*
- *"This course enhanced my understanding of REE and other things related to mining exploration etc"*

Evaluation of Public Events

One of the key objectives of the AGEMERA project is the successful development, planning, and execution of workshops, seminars, and public awareness events regarding critical minerals and metals. So, project partners have

continuously developed and organised public awareness campaigns through seminars and workshops on raw materials at several European sites (Table 3). There were two workshops, three seminars, and three public events until 2nd year reporting (July 2024). In addition, a certificate of attendance has been prepared to be provided to the participants of the events (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Template of the certificate of attendance for the event participants (Vrabie, 2024)

Six residents attended a public event UL arranged in Finland to get local perspectives for the AGEMERA pilot questionnaire research. Thirty doctorate candidates and civil society representatives were introduced to the AGEMERA project through an online seminar hosted by UL. Latitude 66 Cobalt (LAT) and Radai (RAD) organised two seminars. One seminar gathered twelve industry and business partners, and the other seminar hosted fifty citizens, where LAT and RAD discussed exploration work and the EU Critical Raw Materials Act in Kuusamo, Finland.

Two separate seminars were organised in Kuusamo, which drew about fifty people from outlying areas, industry, and business partners. These two-hour interactive events included coffee talks, talks about ongoing exploration projects and their findings, explanations of the EU Critical Raw Materials Act and how it affects national laws, and in-depth drone demos. Furthermore, Latitude 66 Cobalt and RAD arranged three events in October 2023, including one for the media and professional stakeholders, including the Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) and EIT Raw Materials. Later, articles on the planned drone test flights appeared in local and regional newspapers in November and December 2023.

Table 3. Organised public events, seminars and workshops

Date	Type	Involved Partner	Venue / Place	Covered Topics	Target Group	Participants
17.01.2023	Public Event	UL	Finland	AGEMERA pilot questionnaire study: What local people think	Citizens	6
19.01.2023	Seminar	UL	Online	AGEMERA project to the doctoral candidates	Civil Society	30
11.10.2023	Seminar	LAT, RAD	Kuusamo, Finland	Exploration work and results, EU Critical Raw Materials Act	Industry, business partners	12
10.2023	Seminar	LAT, RAD	Kuusamo, Finland	Exploration work and results, EU Critical Raw Materials Act	Citizens	50
30–31.10.2023	Public Event	UO	Rovaniemi, Finland	AGEMERA project, panel, speech, handouts	Wider Audience	120
9.04.2024	Workshop	TT	TalTech, Pärnu County, Estonia	To raise awareness of CRM for high school students in Valga	Civil Society	49
11–12.05.2024	Public Event	BAS	Bulgaria	AGEMERA project and critical and strategic raw materials (CSRМ)	Civil Society	—
6.06.2024	Workshop	TT	TalTech Mektory, Estonia	Role of mineral commodities in the EU: Where does the fork come from?	Civil Society	8

A workshop at TT in Pärnu County, Estonia, aimed to increase the knowledge of forty-nine Valga high school students on CRM. The Geological Institute of Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS) organised a public awareness campaign in Bulgaria focusing on the AGEMERA project and strategic and critical raw materials for civil society. Eight members of civil society participated in a workshop at TalTech Mektory, Estonia, where the topic of mineral commodities and, specifically, “Where does the fork come from?” was discussed. Several target groups, including citizens, members of civil society, business professionals, and students, attended and participated in discussions at these public events, seminars, and workshops.

CONCLUSION

The paper has gathered a summary of the work package - 2 activities focused on the second year of the AGEMERA project with evaluation results and discussion. The pilot and the multi-nation questionnaire survey initiatives have produced data-driven information in the project. Those data have been crucial for the researchers to create well-informed policy recommendations and promote sustainable development in the case study region. At the same time, the overall survey experience would serve as a reference for future

enhancements in comparable initiatives for the following year.

Simultaneously, an international audience was successfully engaged in CRM value chain education with the launch of the online courses “European Critical Raw Materials for the Green and Digital Transition (ECRMs),” produced in collaboration with multiple HEI partners. However, it has also shown potential for greater efficacy in educational projects to improve understanding of critical raw materials.

Furthermore, public awareness initiatives, workshops, and seminars have increased community involvement and comprehension of critical raw materials by fostering conversations among many stakeholders. These initiatives show AGEMERA’s dedication to sustainability and community involvement and helped the researchers create a more practical communication plan and ongoing assessment of the regions.

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